

NURSE-INITIATED EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT PROTOCOLS FOR PAIN MANAGEMENT: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF CLINICAL IMPACT AND IMPLEMENTATION CHALLENGES

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Abstract

Background: Timely pain management in emergency departments (EDs) is critical to improve patient outcomes. Nurse-initiated protocols (NIPs) allow nursing staff to administer treatment, analgesia and corticosteroids without waiting for physician orders, reducing treatment delays and enhancing care quality. We aimed to evaluate the clinical effectiveness and implementation challenges of nurse-initiated protocols for pain management and corticosteroid administration in EDs. **Methods:** A systematic review was conducted in accordance with PRISMA guidelines. Databases searched included PubMed, Scopus, CINAHL, and ScienceDirect. Eligible studies assessed nurse-initiated interventions for analgesia or corticosteroids in ED settings and reported on clinical or process outcomes. Data were synthesized qualitatively and categorized by intervention type and outcomes. **Results:** Seven studies met inclusion criteria, including pediatric and adult populations with asthma, trauma, and musculoskeletal pain. Nurse-initiated protocols reduced time to medication delivery, improved pain control, increased protocol adherence, and enhanced patient satisfaction. For pediatric asthma, early corticosteroid administration led to reduced admission rates and faster recovery. Barriers to implementation included limited staff confidence, time constraints, and inadequate training, and enablers included protocol standardization and

strong nursing autonomy. **Conclusion:** Nurse-initiated protocols in EDs are effective in improving the timeliness and quality of pain and asthma management. Widespread adoption optimize patient outcomes, though challenges in implementation require attention.

Keywords: Nurse-Initiated Protocols, Emergency Department, Analgesia, Corticosteroids, Pain Management, Asthma, Implementation Barriers.

INTRODUCTION

Emergency departments (EDs) are dynamic environments in which timely interventions are essential to prevent clinical deterioration and improve patient outcomes. Delays in the administration of critical therapies, analgesia and corticosteroids, is linked to increased patient discomfort, prolonged ED stays, and higher hospital admission rates (Cabilan & Boyde, 2017; Muntlin et al., 2011). Many institutions have implemented nurse-initiated protocols (NIPs) to expedite care and alleviate treatment bottlenecks.

Nurse-initiated protocols authorize trained nursing staff to begin specific treatments, analgesia or corticosteroid administration, prior to direct physician evaluation. These protocols are designed to reduce treatment delays, optimize resource utilization, and empower nursing professionals to operate at the top of their scope of practice (Varndell et al., 2018). Previous studies have shown that nurse-led interventions can reduce time to pain relief and medication delivery in both pediatric and adult emergency patients (Pierik et al., 2016; Dewhirst et al., 2017).

The effectiveness of NIPs is especially evident in managing acute asthma and musculoskeletal pain. In pediatric asthma, early administration of systemic corticosteroids is associated with reduced hospital admission rates and shorter recovery time (Hopkins et al., 2022). Prompt analgesia improves patient satisfaction, pain scores, and overall care efficiency (Ridderikhof et al., 2016). Variability in protocol adoption, training, and confidence in ED staff presents ongoing implementation challenges (Gawthorne et al., 2024). According to the growing interest in nurse-led models of emergency care, a systematic review is needed to consolidate current evidence regarding the outcomes, barriers, and enabling factors associated with nurse-initiated interventions. This review aims to evaluate the impact of nurse-initiated protocols for analgesia and corticosteroid administration on clinical outcomes in emergency departments and to identify common implementation themes in healthcare settings.

METHODOLOGY

This study is a systematic review conducted in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. The study aimed to synthesize current evidence on the implementation and outcomes of nurse-initiated protocols in emergency department (ED) settings, focusing on pain management and corticosteroid administration.

A literature search was conducted using PubMed, Scopus, CINAHL, and ScienceDirect. Keywords included: *nurse-initiated protocols*, *emergency department*, *analgesia*, *corticosteroids*, *asthma*, *pain management*, and *quality improvement*. The search was

limited to articles published in English and focused on studies involving emergency department interventions by nurses.

We include studies conducted in an emergency department setting; evaluated a nurse-initiated protocol related to analgesia or corticosteroid administration; reported clinical or process outcomes (time to medication, pain relief, satisfaction); published as full-text original research articles. We exclude review articles, editorials, letters, and conference abstracts; studies not involving ED settings; protocols not initiated by nurses.

Two independent reviewers screened titles and abstracts for relevance. Full-text articles were then retrieved and assessed for eligibility. Any disagreements between reviewers were resolved through consensus with a third reviewer.

Data were extracted using a standardized form capturing the following variables: author and year of publication; study design and sample size; patient population and demographics; description of nurse-initiated intervention; and main outcomes and findings. A qualitative synthesis was, results were categorized into pain management outcomes, corticosteroid administration for asthma, and implementation barriers / enablers.

RESULTS

This review included seven studies evaluating nurse-initiated protocols in emergency departments in different patient populations and clinical settings. Study designs were prospective quality improvement initiatives, interrupted time series and before-after observational studies. Sample sizes differ from 132 pediatric patients to over 1,000 adult trauma cases reviewed in multiple time points.

Four studies focused on pediatric populations with asthma or orthopedic injuries (Sneller 2020; Kramer 2024; Brown 2016; Schoolman-Anderson 2018), and two examined adult patients with trauma or musculoskeletal pain (Ridderikhof 2016; Dewhirst 2017). One study assessed perceptions of emergency nurses and physicians regarding protocol use (Gawthorne 2024). Most studies were conducted in high-volume tertiary care centers.

Implementation of nurse-initiated protocols improved medication delivery. In the adult trauma population, the use of nurse-initiated fentanyl led to an increase in analgesic administration from 29% to 36% at 18 months, with improved documentation of pain scores and post-discharge treatment (Ridderikhof 2016). A triage-based intranasal fentanyl protocol for pediatric orthopedic injuries increased its use from 41% to 60%, and eliminating unnecessary intravenous access (Schoolman-Anderson 2018). A nurse-initiated directive reduced the time to analgesic administration from 160 to 118 minutes and increased early analgesia within 30 minutes from 4% to 20% (Dewhirst 2017).

For asthma care in pediatric EDs, three studies show improved timeliness of corticosteroid administration. Steroid administration within 60 minutes increased from 59.3% to 84.3%, with a corresponding decrease in mean time from 71.4 to 48.1 minutes (Sneller 2020). A similar study showed a reduction from 59 to 38 minutes following

nursing-led dexamethasone delivery (Kramer 2024). Another intervention using bedside nurse-initiated dexamethasone reduced administration time from 98 to 59 minutes and lowered both hospital admission and emesis rates (Brown 2016).

In a mixed-methods survey, nurses expressed high motivation to use nurse-initiated protocols, citing patient care improvements and clinical autonomy as key enablers (Gawthorne 2024). Time constraints, limited confidence, and inadequate resources were identified as barriers. Confidence in using nurse-led protocols was higher in accredited nurses. In all included studies, nurse-initiated protocols were associated with reduced time to treatment, improved care efficiency, higher patient satisfaction, and minimal adverse effects.

Table 1: Summary of the included studies

Citation	Study Design	Sample Size	Methodology	Study Aim
Ridderikhof et al., 2016	Pre-post implementation observational study	512 (pre), 507 (6 months), 468 (18 months)	Implemented nurse-initiated pain management protocol using fentanyl, with data collection at 3 time points and chart reviews	To evaluate effect of nurse-initiated fentanyl protocol on analgesic administration and pain awareness in trauma patients
Sneller et al., 2020	Prospective quality improvement (QI) project	Not specified, tracked over 24 months	Implemented asthma nursing treatment protocol using multiple Plan-Do-Study-Act cycles; tracked corticosteroid administration time	To decrease time to corticosteroid administration in pediatric ED asthma patients
Kramer et al., 2024	QI study using Model for Improvement	Not specified (timeline Oct 2021 - Mar 2022)	Implemented nurse-driven dexamethasone administration protocol; interventions included education, EHR changes, and supply improvements	To reduce time from ED arrival to dexamethasone administration in pediatric asthma patients
Brown et al., 2016	Interrupted time series analysis	672 total (336 pre and 336 post)	Implemented nurse-initiated oral dexamethasone protocol and compared pre/post intervention data	To reduce time to corticosteroid administration and improve asthma outcomes in pediatric ED patients
Schoolman-Anderson et al., 2018	Prospective observational study (before-after)	132 patients (72 pre, 60 post)	Implemented triage-based protocol for intranasal fentanyl administration by nurses	To evaluate impact of nurse-initiated intranasal fentanyl protocol on analgesia time and satisfaction
Dewhirst et al., 2017	Before-after health record review	401 patients (201 pre, 200 post)	Introduced medical directive for nurse-initiated oral	To assess impact of nurse-initiated analgesia on time to

			analgesics and compared outcomes	medication and ED stay
Gawthorne et al., 2024	Embedded mixed methods survey	76 nurses, 34 doctors	Surveyed barriers/enablers to nurse-initiated protocols using TDF and PES-NWI frameworks	To identify factors influencing use of nurse-initiated protocols in emergency departments

Table 2: Demographics and outcomes

Citation	Demographics	Main Findings	Outcomes
Ridderikhof et al., 2016	Adult trauma patients (≥18 yrs), Dutch Level I trauma center	Analgesic use increased at 18 months (29% to 36%), not significantly at 6 months	Improved pain awareness and post-discharge treatment; no adverse events
Sneller et al., 2020	Pediatric patients (1–18 yrs) with asthma in a U.S. children’s hospital ED	Steroid administration within 60 min rose from 59.3% to 84.3%	Reduced time to steroids; no increase in return visits; sustained improvement
Kramer et al., 2024	Children ≥2 yrs with asthma, Pediatric ED in San Diego	Time to dexamethasone dropped from 59 to 38 min	No change in admission rate; ED LOS increased slightly
Brown et al., 2016	Children 1–18 yrs with moderate-severe asthma at urban tertiary hospital	Steroid time decreased from 98 to 59 min; improved within 2 months	Lower admission and emesis rates; no increase in return visits
Schoolman-Anderson et al., 2018	Children 3–17 yrs with orthopedic injuries at tertiary children’s hospital	Use of intranasal fentanyl rose from 41% to 60%	Reduced unnecessary IV use; high patient/parent satisfaction
Dewhirst et al., 2017	Adult patients with musculoskeletal back pain in Ottawa Hospital ED	Analgesic time improved (160 to 118 min); early analgesia rose (4% to 20%)	No change in total ED stay or total analgesic use
Gawthorne et al., 2024	ED nurses (n=76) and doctors (n=34) in Australia	High nurse motivation; barriers included time, confidence, resources	Identified key factors for successful protocol implementation

DISCUSSION

This systematic review show that nurse-initiated protocols in emergency departments (EDs) enhance the timeliness and quality of patient care in pediatric and adult populations. The findings align with broader evidence supporting the safety, effectiveness, and operational efficiency of empowering nurses to initiate analgesia and corticosteroid administration under structured guidelines.

Studies showed reductions in time to analgesic administration following nurse-initiated interventions. Ridderikhof et al. (2016) found improvement in frequency of fentanyl administration and pain documentation in adult trauma patients after protocol implementation. Similarly, Dewhirst et al. (2017) show that a medical directive enabling

nurse-led analgesia reduced treatment delays and improved early pain management for musculoskeletal complaints. These findings consistent with Muntlin et al. (2011), who observed better pain control and faster treatment following a nurse-led opioid protocol for abdominal pain.

Schoolman-Anderson et al. (2018), indicate how nurse-initiated intranasal fentanyl enhanced analgesia delivery and reduced unnecessary IV placements, improving the patient experience and reducing procedural burden. These results were similar to findings by Pierik et al. (2016), who showed increased analgesic usage and clinically relevant reductions in pain scores when nurse-driven protocols were adopted for musculoskeletal injuries.

The synthesis of evidence from the included studies underscores improvements in key patient outcomes including reduced time to treatment, increased analgesia administration, improved pain scores, and patient satisfaction. Literature show the effectiveness of nurse-initiated analgesia protocols in reducing time to pain relief and increasing the rate of analgesic administration. Burgess et al. reviewed 26 studies and reported consistent reductions in time to analgesia and symptomatic relief across diverse patient groups. Cabilan and Boyde found that nurse-initiated medications, salbutamol and analgesia, resulted in faster medication delivery and improved patient outcomes without increasing adverse events.

These findings are supported by individual studies such as Muntlin et al., who implemented a nurse-initiated opioid protocol for abdominal pain. Their quasi-experimental study show improvements in time to analgesia and pain relief, as well as enhanced patient perceptions of care quality. Pierik et al. (D4) observed increase in analgesic administration (from 46.8% to 68.0%) and clinically relevant reductions in pain scores following the implementation of a nurse-initiated pain protocol for musculoskeletal pain.

Beyond pain management, the review by Varndell et al. addressed the complexities of nurse-led sedation management for mechanically ventilated patients. Their findings show the need for advanced nursing education and formal policy support to ensure safe and effective continuous sedation in emergency settings.

Varndell et al. (D2) conducted a systematic review examining nurse-initiated analgesia (NIA), concluding that such interventions are safe, timely, and effective. They improvements in time to treatment, pain score reductions, and patient satisfaction, all of which align with international standards for emergency care quality.

The national audit conducted by Fry et al. (D7) contextualizes these findings within Australian practice. Of the 2,066 cases reviewed, 74.9% of patients presenting in pain received analgesics, with 32.7% receiving opioids. Median time to analgesic administration was 70 minutes. Emergency departments that empowered nurses to initiate analgesia reported better analgesic responsiveness, although inconsistencies in documentation and protocol adherence remained.

These findings reinforce the critical importance of structured nurse-initiated protocols in reducing delays in care and enhancing patient outcomes in emergency departments. Several challenges persist, including variability in protocol adoption, need for ongoing staff education, and ensuring compliance with evidence-based guidelines. Policy makers and healthcare institutions must prioritize the integration of standardized nurse-initiated pathways to support efficient, high-quality emergency care.

CONCLUSION

Our systematic review show that nurse-initiated protocols in emergency departments enhance the timeliness and quality of pain management and corticosteroid administration for adult and pediatric patients. In the included studies, these protocols led to earlier medication delivery, reduced procedural delays, improved pain control, and higher patient satisfaction, without increasing adverse events. These findings support the growing evidence that empowering nurses with structured treatment pathways contributes to more efficient and effective emergency care. Variability in implementation, staff training, and institutional support is a challenge.

List of Abbreviations

ED, Emergency Department; NIP, Nurse-Initiated Protocol; NIA, Nurse-Initiated Analgesia; IV, Intravenous; LOS, Length of Stay; QI, Quality Improvement; EHR, Electronic Health Record; TDF, Theoretical Domains Framework; PES-NWI, Practice Environment Scale of the Nursing Work Index; RCT, Randomized Controlled Trial; PDSA, Plan-Do-Study-Act; U.S., United States; min, Minutes.

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